

School Administrators' and Teachers' Preparedness for Inclusive Education in the Elementary Schools of District II, Division of San Carlos City

Jenelyn G. Unabia, MAEd

Graduate Student, Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos, Inc

Rommel S. Marcellana, PhD

Graduate School Instructor, Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos, Inc

Abstract:

Inclusive education refers to an educational method that make sure all learners, regardless of their disabilities, background or learning differences, learn together in the same learning spaces where obstructions are detached and individualized supports are given. This study intended to determine the relationships between school administrators' preparedness and teachers' preparedness for inclusive education. The descriptive-correlational method was used. A total of one hundred seven (107) respondents answered the survey questionnaire regarding school administrators' preparedness and teachers' preparedness in inclusive education. Results revealed that school administrators' and teachers' preparedness demonstrated a very high level of preparedness in all domains. Statistical analysis showed very high and significant correlation between administrators' preparedness and teachers' preparedness, indicating that strong administrative support substantially enhances teachers' capacity to implement inclusive practices. While the district has effectively established many inclusive practices, enhancements are still needed in infrastructure accessibility and the availability of assistive devices.

Strengthening leadership skills and resource allocation is possible to further uplift teachers' performance in addressing the needs of learners with disabilities. Overall, results indicate that District II schools are well prepared for inclusive education but must continue in developing resources and facility accessibility to ensure equitable, approachable and fully inclusive learning

environments. The output of this study is the Professional Development Training Program for all school administrators and teachers.

Keywords: School Administrators' Preparedness, Teacher's Preparedness, Inclusive Education, San Carlos City, Philippines, Quantitative.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Inclusive education ensures that all learners, regardless of their capabilities, disabilities, background and status learn together in regular classrooms with the needed support to succeed (UNESCO, 2021). According to Ainscow and Liasidou 2021, emphasized that children with special needs are rightful members of the school community, entitled to equal access to resources and social interactions, which strengthens both academic achievement and social inclusion.

From a global perspective, inclusive education is commonly recognized as important for realizing equitable education for learners with disabilities (UNESCO, 2020). According to Mohd Yusof Zulkefli et al., 2024, the ability of schools to implement inclusive practices depends greatly on how well teachers and school administrators are prepared. In many perspective, even though policies exist to promote inclusion, gaps persist in training, resource allocation, leadership support and collaboration.

In regional perspectives, studies from Saudi Arabia, Pakistan, Malaysia, and elsewhere point to similar patterns: pre-service teachers or in-service teachers often have theoretical knowledge but weaker skills in implementing individualized plans, differentiated instruction, and inclusive classroom environment (Mendoza and Heymann 2024).

In Philippines, recent studies in secondary schools and junior high schools reveal that teachers self-report "moderate" levels of preparedness in areas such as instructional methods, collaboration, classroom management, behavioural interventions and transition planning, but also report gaps in specific training, planning, and resource availability (Alido et al., 2023; Sabanal, et al., 2025).

While research on inclusive education and the role of educators and school administrators in promoting inclusive practices has been conducted, few studies have explored this topic extensively, there remains limited research that particularly focuses on the preparedness levels of both administrators and teachers within the District II, Division of San Carlos City. The literature that is currently available frequently focuses on administrative policies or only addresses teacher preparedness without examining how both groups work in tandem to provide inclusive education.

Furthermore, the alignment of administrative leadership, training opportunities, and support systems with teachers' actual skills and competencies in implementing inclusive education is rarely examined in prior research. This makes a significant gap in understanding whether preparedness of administrators and teachers is interrelated or if inconsistencies in their preparedness hinder inclusive practices.

This study is significant because school administrators and teachers play a different but equally important roles in implementing inclusive education, yet their level of preparedness differ. Administrators are expected to provide leadership, policies and resources while teachers need the ability to handle diverse learners in the classroom. When one group is more equipped than the other, inclusive education becomes challenging to convey effectively. By determining the gap between their preparedness, the study aims to identify what support, training or enhancements are required so that both administrators and teachers can work amicably to better serve the learners with disabilities.

This study seeks to assess the level of readiness exhibited by school administrators and teachers for inclusive education in the public elementary schools of District II, Division of San Carlos City. The goal of the study is to gain a better understanding and determine the level preparedness of both administrators and teachers in terms of policies, leadership skills, resource allocation, professional development, infrastructure, knowledge, instructional skills, attitudes and collaboration that affects the successful provision of inclusive education. This research seeks to determine the relationship of administrators' and teachers preparedness in inclusive education. This study's findings could serve as a basis for developing professional qualifications.

Literature Review

In this part of the research covers both local and international issues relating to school administrators and teachers' readiness for inclusive learning.

School Administrators

According to Wang & Zhang (2021), Principals act as key drivers of inclusion, as their guidance and support significantly enhance teachers' professional competence and commitment to inclusive education.

Based on the study of De Matthews et al., (2021), the study viewed at the attitudes, procedures, and difficulties related to significant change in inclusive schools. The results highlight the importance of principals in creating inclusive schools and the manner in which administrators' attempts to promote inclusion are impacted by factors such as immigrant status, language, family history, race, and disability.

Although each administrator faced numerous obstacles and acknowledged the previously mentioned causes, their perspectives and methods for establishing inclusive schools varied. While certain leadership techniques more closely mirrored social justice leadership techniques, others were in line with studies on effective school leadership. They said that despite resistance and barriers to meaningful transformation, administrators should evaluate a wide range of issues in order to establish inclusive schools and utilize a wide range of techniques.

According to Lambrecht et al., (2022), the study examined the effect of school leadership on implementing inclusive education. Research showed that collaboration structures were crucial for implementing individualized education plans. The impact of transformational leadership on implementing individualized education plans was completely mitigated by the collaboration structures. Additionally, they had a moderately beneficial impact on the way that individualized education plans were implemented.

According to Bansal (2021), the research findings showed that while principals had a decent understanding of inclusion, they did not believe that schools were prepared to accommodate students with disabilities. Lack of infrastructure and resources, special education and support services, parent non-cooperation, large class sizes, and behavioral problems with children with disabilities were the main concerns raised.

The research underlined the need to train instructors, provide special education and other support services, upgrade the physical facilities on the school site, and make teaching-learning resources, materials, and equipment available for the benefit of students with disabilities. A culture of acceptance, collaboration, and creativity will be fostered by principals who have a clear vision and have received training in inclusive technique. They will also encourage innovative ideas for the implementation of inclusive education.

In Indonesia, Simorangkir (2021) documented persistent gaps in facility availability and resource provision across inclusive schools, showing that inadequate materials, staffing, and accessibility features constrain administrators' capacity to meet inclusive education standards.

Continuous professional Development is a capacity multiplier for inclusive schools. A multi-site virtual professional development study by Montalbano et al.,(2024) found statistically significant gains in knowledge of accommodations and modifications, Universal Design for Learning, co-teaching, and differentiation, demonstrating that well-designed professional development models can efficiently upskill school-based professionals, including administrators.

A systematic review by Holmqvist & Lelinge (2021) reports that collaborative professional development improves attitudes toward inclusion, even if evidence on student learning effects is still emerging, supporting the idea that professional development strengthens readiness and dispositions needed for implementation.

In addition, based on the study of White and Rojo-Ramos et al., (2022), highlighted that when school leaders actively promote inclusive practices and invest in professional development, mentoring, and collaborative learning, they provide teachers with essential competencies such as differentiation strategies and teamwork skills to effectively handle diverse classrooms.

Inclusive schools requires many resources; administrators are more prepared when they can allocate funds, staffing, assistive technologies, and time equitably. Based on the study of Duan & Dubae (2024), claimed that persistent discrimination in resource distribution weaken educational equality and hinder administrators' ability to deliver inclusion and they advocate needs-based funding and transparent allocation to empower school leaders.

Similarly, Dy and Galigao (2025), synthesize global models and conclude that strategic, equitable distribution is related with better learners outcomes, supporting that strong resource stewardship is a trademark of preparedness.

According to Simorangkir (2021), documented the gaps between supervisory standards and concrete facility accessibility in inclusive schools (e.g., ramps, toilets), signifying that lack of infrastructure compels administrators' capacity to provide inclusive commitments. The UNESCO (2020) background paper details universal design elements and emphasized implementation difficulties; it commends submission tools that administrators can influence to develop physical accessibility and safety for all learners.

According to Steed et al. (2024), highlighted that administrators give importance to inclusion and make sure access to resources are possible but they still report limited funding and shortages of assistive devices and personnel.

Furthermore, according to the study of Grissom et al., (2021) found that although school administrators may not directly teach students, their decisions and actions indirectly impact learning by shaping teacher performance, school culture, and resource allocation. Strong leadership, therefore, becomes a foundation upon which inclusive education initiatives are built and sustained.

Additionally, according to Grissom et al., (2021), study found that even if school leaders may not directly teach learners, their decisions and actions ultimately impact learning by influencing teacher performance, school culture and resource allocation. Strong management, therefore, becomes a basis upon which inclusive education initiatives are made and continued.

School administrators are the main governing body, instructional leaders, and coordinators of inclusive practices across the entire school. They are essential in inclusive education and their readiness has a significant impact on teachers' level of preparedness.

Fabunan and Cabal (2025) reported on the degree of proficiency of school administrators in implementing inclusive education. As shown in research effective instructional leadership is important to make sure inclusive education is promoted in schools. School Administrators established excellent proficiency in collaborating with teachers, reviewing student output and following the school policies that prioritize collaboration and respect for individual differences.

Additionally, school administrators may be offered ongoing professional development programs to enhance their abilities in inclusive instruction. Training should to focused curriculum enhancement, differentiated instruction and using technology to assist a diverse learners. School administrators should be advised to embrace forms of collaborative leadership that includes teachers, parents and community members when making decisions.

According to Aragao (2025), effective school leaders must be morally decent, accountable, flexible, wise decision makers, creative thinkers and capable of inspiring others. The study highlights the importance of shared leadership practices and unified commitment among stakeholders in building a motivated and morally grounded school atmosphere where both staff and learners feel empowered. In addition, study suggests that strong agreement on inclusive strategies like curriculum modifications, environmental adjustments, collaboration, individualized support and nurturing a positive school culture reflects the principal's dedication to address diverse learners' needs.

According to a 2025 study conducted in Iloilo by Palma, school administrators exhibit resilience, inventiveness, and effective techniques while putting inclusive education into practice. Along with technological integration and future-focused leadership abilities, working together of special education and general education educators emerged as a crucial tactic. Managing change, crises, and resource constraints, all of which are crucial for inclusive education in the Philippine context that requires resilience.

Based on the study of Tagyamon et al., (2025), the study highlighted that inclusive education in the Philippines is strongly supported by existing policies, but implementation varies across schools. They also emphasized that inclusive practices become effective when there is clear policy direction, supportive leadership, and proper monitoring.

According to Lagura & Tubasis (2023), a study that assesses the readiness and inclusive education practices of teachers and school administrators in Agusan del Norte Division, Caraga Region, Philippines. The findings demonstrate that administrators and teachers were prepared for inclusive education in terms of school climate, student support, and teacher attitudes, skills, and knowledge since inclusive education was extensively implemented and had proper planning. As a result, the findings of this study may help all schools adopt inclusive education in a more meaningful way.

According to a study conducted in Pasig City by Javier (2023), school administrators gave the implementation of inclusive education a high rating for difficulties, particularly in areas like teacher skills, classroom management, infrastructure, instructional materials, and financial resources. Teachers and school administrators had parallel beliefs about these challenges, suggesting that there are primary problems that prevent all schools from being well prepared.

Furthermore, even while training programs and instructional materials were only assessed as somewhat successful, school administrators emphasized the need for better institutional support, integrated capacity-building activities, and better budget allocation. These results demonstrate the importance of administrative readiness in facilitating consistent implementation across various educational contexts.

Moreover, even though training programs and instructional materials were only assessed as slightly successful, school administrators highlights the need for better support, combined capacity building activities and improved budget allocation. These results revealed the significance of administrative readiness in facilitating consistent implementation across numerous educational settings.

According to the study of Lingayon (2025) identified resource constraints, including insufficient material resources and accessibility equipment, as recurring national limitations. He also noted that many schools cannot fully comply with DepEd guidelines due to inadequate funding and infrastructure.

Teachers

Since teachers are in charge of putting inclusive practices into practice in the classroom, they are essential to this process (Sharma et al., 2022). It is frequently noted that teacher preparedness, which includes knowledge, attitudes, and instructional competence, is a critical component of the successful implementation of inclusion (Forlin, 2020; Loreman, 2021).

According to a study by Donath et al. (2023), professional development has a moderately positive impact on teachers' instructional skills. This suggests that when teachers receive structured training that incorporates practice-based and active learning components, their instructional readiness significantly improves.

According to Singh et al., (2020), the study investigate the attitude of the teacher's towards inclusive education. Educator attitudes toward inclusive education range from mild to positive, according to the study's findings. The research indicates that pre-service teachers are more open to inclusive education than in- service teachers, and the attitudes of male and female educators are almost identical. Moreover Furthermore, teachers' genders do not affect their attitudes towards inclusive education. According to the researcher's findings, urban teachers were more inclined towards inclusive education than their rural counterparts.

Yadav (2024) noted that teacher attitudes are critical because inclusive education requires willingness, openness, and commitment to support diverse learners. The study underlined that teacher preparedness is deeply tied to their belief in the value of inclusion and equitable education affirming that positive attitudes correlate with stronger implementation.

One of the best indicators of a teacher's preparation for inclusion is professional development (PD). Although there is currently no long-term data on the effects on students, Holmqvist & Lelinge (2021) found that collaborative professional development boosts positive attitudes and enhances teachers' capacity to engage in inclusive practices. The importance of teacher cooperation as a means of problem-solving and shared learning is emphasized in their review.

Donath et al. (2023) shown that professional development programs result in favorable changes in attitudes toward inclusion, modest impacts on teaching abilities, and big effects on knowledge. According to the study, instructors are much more equipped to fulfill the needs of diverse students in inclusive classrooms when they get consistent, high-quality, and practically applicable professional development as opposed to isolated, one-time seminars.

To improve teachers' proficiency in inclusive education, continuous professional development, or CPD, is crucial. El Deen (2023) discovered that mentors' methods for evaluating teachers' performance and development differ, highlighting the difficulty of assessing professional development. Similar to this, Sebsibe et al. (2023) highlighted that a lack of suitable training modalities is the root cause of many instructional challenges, highlighting the necessity of supervisory assistance that encourages ongoing skill development.

Additionally, Holmqvist & Lelinge (2021) found that participation in professional development significantly enhances teachers' attitudes toward inclusion. Interestingly, their study also revealed that teachers with the most positive attitudes show higher risks of burnout, indicating that attitude support must be accompanied by structural resources and psychological well-being.

A study of Larios & Zetlin (2023), suggested that there should be a sustained shift toward teacher preparation programs and school district staff collaborating to: (1) create and implement interactive, relevant professional development; and (2) work together beyond the initial years of teaching to support teachers in staying up to date in their field. These findings have shed light on some of the advantages and difficulties instructors face when they are provided with opportunity to work together to build the abilities and mindset necessary to successfully meet the requirements of every student.

Based on the study in China by Yousefi, Wang, and Mullick (2025) revealed that teacher efficacy in collaboration is the strongest predictor of successful inclusive practices, outperforming even instructional skills and behavior management abilities.

Furthermore, Holmqvist & Lelling (2021) highlighted that collaborative professional development fosters collective responsibility and strengthens school wide inclusive practices. A shared professional learning environment enhances teachers' confidence and preparedness, reinforcing that inclusion is most effective when teachers work with rather than in isolation.

In a study conducted by Cola et al., (2025) at Sogod Central School in Southern Leyte, they examined whether teachers were ready and willing to accommodate students with special educational needs (LSENs). Most teachers were categorized by their level of readiness and willingness to accommodate LSENs in their classrooms, as per the survey. Their level of preparedness, particularly in terms of instructional strategies and pedagogical knowledge, had the strongest influence on their acceptance. When teachers are confident in their skills, they are more open to inclusive approaches. However, there are still challenges, especially when handling more complex LSEN situations and the lack of trustworthy resources and training.

Effective inclusive education is built on the knowledge of teachers. Teachers had a modest understanding of inclusive education, especially when it came to inclusive teaching methods and managing students with a range of needs, according to a 2025 research by Vergara et al. Significant knowledge gaps still exist, nevertheless, in areas like implementing Individualized Education Plans (IEPs), adaptive technology, and Universal Design for Learning (UDL). These discrepancies point to the necessity of additional specialized training to improve educators' academic and practical comprehension of inclusive teaching frameworks.

In a similar vein, Englis et al. (2025) highlighted that while educators comprehend the idea and significance of inclusion, many find it difficult to convert this academic knowledge into practical classroom procedures. Their results highlight the necessity for continuous learning to facilitate practical implementation.

Teachers' readiness in inclusive education environments is largely dependent on their instructional competency. According to Vergara et al., (2025), teachers demonstrated strong classroom management abilities and an ability to respectfully handle diverse behaviours. However, deficiencies were identified in adapting instruction for varied learning needs, integrating technology, and employing UDL based strategies and skills that are essential in modern inclusive classrooms.

Based on the study of Cola et al., (2025), findings discovered that the most highly ranked aspect of teacher readiness was instructional skills, which indicated that teachers felt most comfortable creating courses, adjusting their methods, and employing tactics for a variety of learners. Instructional strategies were strongly correlated with acceptance of inclusion, suggesting that better instructional skill reinforces willingness to teach inclusively.

In parallel, Sabanal et al., (2025) further revealed that instructional practice was an area of strength, with teachers showing capability in behaviour management, collaboration, and designing supportive instructional environments. However, the study highlighted gaps in advanced instructional knowledge such as UDL and adaptive technologies, which affected the full implementation of inclusive instruction.

Sabanal et al, (2025) found that educational achievement and training were more important factors than personal background in their study; therefore, they postulated this to have direct impact on the competencies required for inclusive education. Teachers who had received training in inclusive practices and had more advanced degrees were particularly well-equipped to carry out inclusive education. In order to provide instructors the information, abilities, and useful tactics they need to

successfully address the various demands of their students, this realization highlighted the necessity of thorough, continuous professional development. One significant discovery was the discrepancy between teachers' favorable opinions of inclusive education and their capacity to successfully apply these sentiments in the classroom.

Furthermore, it was challenging to put the favourable judgments of many instructors into practice, which highlights the need of applied, practical training. In the conclusion, the study confirmed how important it is to give educators practical tools for inclusive education so that effective, inclusive teaching strategies may support healthy attitudes.

Teachers must collaborate in order to be prepared, especially when working with different students. According to Vergara et al. (2025), teachers saw teamwork as a strength in managing inclusive classrooms and felt confident working with colleagues and other stakeholders. Better classroom management, problem-solving, and the exchange of inclusive practices are all facilitated by this partnership.

Synthesis

The literature and studies mentioned above gave a view of what the present study covered and how it was considered more effective. It opened with the school administrators' preparedness in terms of policies, leadership skills, professional development, resource allocation and infrastructure and teachers' preparedness in terms of knowledge, instructional skills, professional development, attitudes and collaboration.

This study was relevant as it would evaluate the current circumstances of educators and school administrators in the Department of Education, particularly in the San Carlos City Division. DepEd may utilize the study's results to create development programs and make policy decisions.

Notably, school administrators are crucial to the success of inclusive education. According to studies, administrators in the Philippines who support teachers, foster teamwork, and exhibit strong leadership contribute to the establishment of inclusive schools. To effectively mentor teachers and manage issues such as a lack of resources, finance, and facilities, they require training, tools, and exact procedures. Implementing inclusive education is made simpler by effective resource management, strong leadership, and cooperation with parents and educators.

Foreign studies support these findings. They demonstrate how administrators play a crucial role in promoting inclusion by assisting educators in developing their abilities and confidence. However, large class numbers and a lack of resources are also problems for many schools overseas. According to research, schools perform better when principals foster collaboration, offer ongoing professional development, and guarantee equitable resource distribution. Overall, research conducted locally and abroad agree that for school administrators to successfully adopt inclusive education, they need to be well-prepared, well-trained, and well-supported.

Local studies show that teachers are moderately to highly prepared and receptive to inclusion, as to instructional skills, differentiating tasks, adjusting techniques, and controlling behaviour have most strongly linked to acceptance of inclusive practices. In the lack of adequate resources, coaching, and time, many teachers struggle to incorporate good attitudes into routine classroom practice, and there are still a lot of unanswered questions, especially in the areas of UDL, adaptive technology, and IEP implementation. Training and academic performance influence preparedness more than demographics, suggesting that targeted, continuous, and useful professional development including lesson study, assisted execution, and classroom based practice is crucial. Working together with stakeholders and colleagues is another relative strength that fosters problem-solving and shared ownership of learner support.

International research also corroborate these conclusions. They demonstrate how having the appropriate mindset, sufficient knowledge, and effective teaching techniques helps instructors

become more inclusive. Excellent and ongoing training is very beneficial to instructors. It enhances their knowledge, fortifies their ability to instruct, and improves their attitudes toward inclusivity. Nevertheless, studies also caution that even when training is beneficial, educators who are very dedicated to inclusion may experience fatigue or burnout. This means schools must give teachers proper support, like reasonable workloads, access to resources, and help from specialists, so they can stay prepared and take care of their well-being.

Theoretical Framework

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1997) and Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979) serve as the foundation for this investigation. According to Bandura's thesis, people's performance is influenced by their self-efficacy, or belief in their own skills. Teachers are more likely to develop, use, and maintain inclusive teaching practices if they think they can effectively instruct students with special needs. Their self-efficacy is influenced by their prior experiences, education, and assistance from co-workers and school administrators. High self-efficacy school leaders are more likely to encourage teacher development, implement inclusive policies, and make sure that resources are allocated appropriately. They influence the culture and atmosphere of the school by acting as role models for inclusive leadership. Preparedness is predicted by self-efficacy. To be genuinely effective, educators and administrators must have confidence in their capacity to manage inclusive environments.

The microsystem (classroom), mesosystem (school), and exosystem (school policies) are some of the levels of impact on a learner's development that are highlighted in Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979). It emphasizes how the learning environment and the experiences of kids with special needs are directly impacted by the readiness and cooperation of educators and administrators.

Since self-efficacy directly reflects readiness, these two theories are both advantageous and pertinent to our investigation. Teachers and administrators are better prepared when they have greater faith in their abilities, expertise, and capacity to oversee inclusive environments. The psychological underpinnings for comprehending why preparation differs and how it may be enhanced by instruction, experience, and leadership support are therefore provided by Bandura's theory. The achievement of inclusive education depends on cooperation at all levels of the school environment; it cannot be achieved only in the classroom.

According to Bronfenbrenner's theory, the whole learning environment for kids with special needs is shaped by the readiness of administrators and teachers working together. The ecological system weakens and inclusive behaviors are jeopardized if either group is unprepared.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The framework demonstrates how the readiness of educators and school officials affects the adoption of inclusive education. Administrator preparedness reflected in policies, leadership skills, resource allocation, professional development, and infrastructure provides the structural and managerial support needed for inclusion. Teacher preparedness, which includes knowledge, instructional skills, attitudes, professional development, and collaboration, represents their capacity to deliver inclusive practices in the classroom.

These two inputs are assessed to determine their levels and examine the relationship between administrative and teacher preparedness in inclusive education. Findings from these assessments guide the formulation of a professional development training program aimed at strengthening both administrative and instructional readiness for inclusive education.

Statement of the Problem

This study examined the administrators' and teachers' readiness for inclusive education in the Elementary Schools of District II, Division of San Carlos City. To guide this study, the following questions will be addressed:

1. What is the level of preparedness of school administrators' preparedness for inclusive education in terms of:
 - a. policies;

- b. leadership skills;
 - c. resource allocation;
 - d. professional development; and
 - e. infrastructure?
2. What is the level of teachers' preparedness for inclusive education in terms of:
 - a) knowledge;
 - b) instructional skills;
 - c) attitudes;
 - d) professional development; and
 - e) collaboration?
 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of school administrators' preparedness and level of teachers' preparedness in inclusive education?
 4. Based on the salient findings, what training program may be proposed?

Statement of Hypothesis

H₀₁. There is no significant relationship between the level of school administrators' preparedness and level of teachers' preparedness in inclusive education.

Significance of the study

Specifically, the results of the study are useful to the following persons:

School Administrators. The findings of the research may provide valuable insights into their current level of preparedness in implementing inclusive education and highlights areas where further development or support may be needed.

Teachers. The findings of the study could provide a clear indication of their current level of readiness to manage learners with diverse needs in an inclusive classroom setting.

Learners with special needs. The results of the study may help learners with special needs receive equitable access to quality education, individualized interventions, and opportunities to participate meaningfully alongside their peers.

Guardians/Parents. The results of the study the study empowers parents by highlighting the importance of collaboration between home and school.

Future Researchers. This may give future researchers a foundational reference on the preparedness of school administrators and teachers in implementing inclusive learning.

Scope of the Study

The study examines how well prepared teachers and school administrators are to work with students who have special needs in inclusive classrooms in District II, Division of San Carlos City's public elementary schools. The study will be carried out in the 2025–2026 academic year. The study will use a quantitative descriptive-correlational design. The respondents include 11 school administrators (principals and assistant principals) and 96 regular classroom teachers.

The administrators' preparedness is assessed in terms of policies, leadership skills, resource allocation, professional development, and infrastructure while the teachers' preparedness is measured in terms of knowledge and understanding, instructional skills, attitudes, professional development, and collaboration. Additionally, the research investigates the connection between the readiness of teachers and administrators, as well as the significant correlation between teachers'

readiness and the assistance provided by administrators in managing learners with special needs. Survey questionnaires will be the main method of data collection in this quantitative descriptive-correlational approach. Only the indicators listed are included by the study, which is restricted to the designated respondents in the district; factors outside of these parameters are not.

Definition of Terms

Understanding the basic terms of this study is essential to establish communication between the researcher and the readers. With this in mind, the basic terms used in this research work are hereby defined operationally.

Attitudes. Teachers' openness, willingness, and commitment to teach learners with diverse needs, measured by Likert-scale statements reflecting acceptance and support.

Collaboration. Refers to the process in which school administrators, teachers, support staff, parents, and the community work together through shared planning, communication, decision-making, and problem-solving to support inclusive education.

Inclusive Education. Refers to the implementation of teaching practices, school policies, support systems, and accommodations for learners with disabilities, as described and measured through the survey indicators related to teachers' and school administrators' preparedness.

Infrastructure. Refers to the availability and accessibility of school facilities supporting inclusion (ramps, SPED-friendly classrooms, assistive devices), measured by respondents' perceptions of completeness and functionality.

Instructional Skills. Refers to the teachers' ability to use differentiated instruction, accommodations, and modifications for diverse learners, measured using Likert-scale items.

Knowledge. Refers to the teachers' understanding of inclusive education concepts, laws, teaching strategies, and learners' diverse needs, measured through self-assessment using a Likert scale.

Leadership Skills. Refers to the degree to which administrators demonstrate inclusive leadership (decision-making, support, communication), measured using Likert-scale items assessing leadership actions that promote inclusive practices.

Preparedness. Refers to the readiness of teachers and school administrators in effectively handling learners with special needs in inclusive education, as measured by specific indicators in the survey questionnaire.

Professional Development. Participation in trainings, workshops, mentoring, and continuous learning related to inclusive education, measured through frequency and perceived usefulness.

Policies. Refers to the extent to which administrators formulate, implement, and monitor inclusive education policies, measured through a Likert scale questionnaire on policy clarity, compliance, and alignment with DepEd guidelines.

Resource Allocation. Refers to the adequacy and prioritization of resources (budget, materials, manpower) provided for inclusive education, measured through respondents' ratings on availability and sufficiency.

School Administrators. Refers to the school principal and assistant school principals of inclusive schools in District II, Division of San Carlos City, who are responsible for policies, leadership, and support in implementing inclusive education.

CHAPTER 2

METHODOLOGY

Chapter II discusses the methodological aspects of the study, including research design; respondents and instruments; data collection process; analysis procedure; statistical treatment; and consideration of ethics.

Research Design

In this study, the research design was descriptive-correlational. The objective of the descriptive component is to examine the level of readiness of school leaders and educators in inclusive education by examining key areas such as policies, leadership skills, resource allocation, professional development, instructional skills, knowledge, attitudes, and collaboration. The correlational component explores the relationships between administrators' preparedness and teachers' preparedness in inclusive education. This design enables the identification of patterns, associations, and significant predictors that contribute to effective inclusive education practices.

Respondents of the study

The study included 11 school administrators and 96 classroom teachers who will be conducting classes in Public Elementary schools of District II, Division of San Carlos City, Negros Occidental for the academic year 2025-2026. They were taken in total enumeration. Data presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents

Schools	Number of Teachers	%
A	22	20.56%
B	12	11.22 %
C	10	9.35%
D	15	14.02 %
E	9	8.41 %
G	9	8.41 %
H	6	5.61 %
I	4	3.74 %
J	6	5.61 %
K	8	7.48 %
L	6	5.61 %
TOTAL	107	100 %

Research Instrument

The study used a survey questionnaire created by the researcher as the main instrument, consisting of two parts: the first measured the level of preparedness and its relationship of school administrators in supporting inclusive education in terms of policies, leadership skills, resource allocation, professional development, and infrastructure, while the second assessed the level of preparedness and its relationship of teachers in handling students with disabilities in terms of knowledge and understanding, instructional skills, attitudes, professional development, and collaboration. Each item was rated using a five-point Likert scale: (5) Strongly Agree, (4) Agree, (3) Neutral, (2) Disagree, (1) Strongly Disagree.

Validity of the instrument

The validity findings revealed that the instrument had strong test qualities. The aggregate mean from the Good and Scates content validation was 4.69, which is regarded as Excellent, shows that the experts' panel thought the items were clear, accurate, and indicative of the intended structures. According to expert judgment, the items' essentiality and relevance are confirmed by the Lawshe Content Validity Ratio (CVR) results, which show that all 25 items were kept, with the majority

obtaining a CVR of 1.00 and a Content Validity Index (CVI) of 0.96, exceeding the acceptable minimum of 0.78. These results are consistent with Lynn's (1986) assertion that strong representativeness and content adequacy in instrument construction are reflected in high CVR and CVI values.

Reliability of the instrument

The reliability instrument has extremely high internal consistency and very little measurement error, according to the reliability test's Cronbach's alpha of .986, which is considered outstanding. This degree of dependability is consistent with the standards set out by Tavakol and Dennick (2011), who contend that coefficients near 1.00 indicate substantial homogeneity among items, and George and Mallery (2003), who characterize alpha values above .90 as exhibiting great internal coherence. Together, the remarkably high validity and reliability ratings attest to the questionnaire's conceptual accuracy, statistical soundness, and suitability for assessing the study's focus variables.

Data Collection Procedure

Prior to data collection, the Schools Division Office, district supervisors, and the respective principals of District II were consulted for permission to conduct the research study. Once approved, the validated survey questionnaires were personally distributed to the target respondents, who were teachers and school principals. The aim of the study was explained to the respondents, and they were guaranteed the privacy of their answers. To answer the study objectives, the gathered data was meticulously tallied, arranged, and examined using the proper statistical tools.

Data Analysis Procedure

Both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were employed to analyze the survey questionnaires. To evaluate the level of preparedness of school administrators, descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations (SDs), frequencies, and percentages were used to determine policy readiness, leadership skills, resource allocation, professional development and infrastructure, and preparedness of teachers for their knowledge, instructional skills, attitudes, professional growth and collaboration.

The correlation between the level of administrators' and teachers' readiness was tested using the Pearson r correlation coefficient.

The significant relationship between school administrators' and teachers' preparedness were analyzed with teacher preparedness as the dependent variable and the various aspects of administrative support as independent variables.

Finally, to identify gaps and design a proposed training program, descriptive analysis was conducted, and if the effectiveness of the program was evaluated. All statistical tests having a difference or relationship was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Statistical Treatment

To tackle the specific research problems numbered 1 and 2, which seek to assess the preparedness levels of school administrators regarding policies, leadership abilities, resource distribution, professional growth, and infrastructure, as well as the preparedness levels of teachers concerning knowledge, instructional competencies, attitudes, professional development, and collaboration in inclusive education, percentages and weighted means were employed using the following formula:

Percentage:

$$\% = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

Where:

% = percentage

f = frequency

n = number of cases

100 = constant value

Weighted mean

$$W \bar{X} = \frac{S_1 (W_5) + S_2 (W_4) + S_3 (W_3) + S_4 (W_2) + S_5 (W_1)}{N}$$

Where:

w \bar{x} = weighted mean

S = responses

W = weighted assigned to the scale

N= number of cases

These tables were used as arbitrary references to interpret the weighted mean values.

Table 2. School Administrators' and Teachers' Preparedness Level

SCALE	MEAN RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.20 - 5.0	Strongly Agree
4	3.40 -4.19	Agree
3	2.60-3.39	Neutral
2	1.80 - 2.59	Disagree
1	1.0 -1.79	Strongly Disagree

For research question number 3 on “Is there a significant relationships between the level of school administrators’ preparedness and level of teachers’ preparedness in inclusive education? the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used with the formula:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

r_{xy} = Pearson r

n = total number of subject-respondent

$\sum x$ = Summation of x or variable x (School Administrators’ Preparedness)

$\sum y$ = Summation of y or variable y (Teachers’ Preparedness)

$\sum xy$ = Summation of x and y or variable x and y

$\sum x^2$ = Summation of squared variable x

$\sum y^2$ = Summation of squared variable y

The Reference Table was used for the interpretation of r_{xy} results.

Table 3. The Reference Table

Coefficient Correlation	Interpretation
$\pm 0.91-1.00$	Very High Correlation; Very Dependable Relationship
$\pm 0.71-0.90$	High Correlation; Marked Relationship
$\pm 0.41-0.70$	Moderate Correlation; Substantial Relationship
$\pm 0.21- 0.40$	Low Correlation; Definite but small relationship
Less than ± 0.20	Very low correlation

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that the study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards of research. Before the data was collected, the Division Superintendent of San Carlos City and school district supervisors and principals of the participating inclusive schools obtained consent. The purpose of the study was made clear to respondents who were invited to participate in the survey, as they had a choice to do so.

Informed Consent

To ensure that their participation is entirely voluntary and not imposed on others, an informed consent form was provided to the respondents before the questionnaire was distributed. The study's purpose and method were also communicated to them. Participants were given the option to decline participation in their research, provided that they did not feel uncomfortable answering the questionnaire, and could be fined during the study period. Additionally, participants were advised against withdrawing from the investigation.

Vulnerability of Research Participants

The researcher paid close attention to the respondents' rights and well-being. To establish true voluntarism, the conditions regarding the respondents' rights were thoroughly clarify. It was made clear to the respondents that their involvement in the study would have no impact on their performance ratings or the renewal of their contract terms, and that they would not lose any benefits as a result of their participation.

Privacy and Confidentiality

The information acquired was kept private in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. No information that revealed the respondents' identities would be disseminated or published without their explicit consent, unless it is required to preserve their rights or welfare. The raw information obtained from them was stored in print and online documents which are secured against illegal access and use and disposed of properly within a set time frame. The respondents were assured that the information they provided would be kept private and that no information about their names would be released. The data and information of the respondents were collected and maintained anonymously, with no identifying variables that might be used to link the data to the individual. The respondents were told how long the data would be retained, where it would be stored, and how it would be deleted via electronic data deletion.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter shows the results, analysis and interpretation of data gathered from the questionnaires and documents in relation to the particular problems and hypothesis of this research. There are 13 tables presented in this chapter.

Table 4. Level of Preparedness of School Administrators in inclusive education in terms of Policies

Indicator	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		TOTAL		w \bar{x}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1. The school has clear policies that support the implementation of inclusive education.	80	74.77	25	23.36	2	1.87	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.73	SA
2. Inclusive education policies are regularly updated.	76	71.03	26	24.30	5	4.67	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.66	SA
3. Policies addressing learners with special needs are effectively communicated to teachers.	78	72.90	19	17.76	10	9.35	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.64	SA
4. The school ensures that policies align with DepEd guidelines on inclusion.	83	77.57	22	20.56	2	1.87	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.76	SA
5. Administrators strictly monitor compliance with inclusive education policies.	76	71.03	24	22.43	7	6.54	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.64	SA
Total/General w\bar{x}	393	73.46	116	21.68	26	4.86	0	0	0	0	535	100	4.69	SA

Legend:

- 5 4.20 - 5.0 Strongly Agree 2 1.80 - 2.59 Disagree
 4 3.40 -4.19 Agree 1 1.0 -1.79 Strongly Disagree
 3 2.60-3.39 Neutral

The survey findings in table 4, revealed that the level of school administrators in terms of policies generally held positive view as evidence by their weighted mean score of 4.69. Notably, the highest weighted mean of 4.76 indicating the school ensures that policies align with Deped Guidelines on inclusion. On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean score was recorded 4.64 declaring that policies address learners with special needs are effectively communicated and administrators strictly monitor compliance with inclusive education. This finding agreed with Tagyamon et al. (2025) study which emphasized that successful implementation depends on clear policy direction at the school level.

Table 5. Level of Preparedness of School Administrators in inclusive education in terms of Leadership Skills

Indicator	Strongly Agree = 5		Agree = 4		Neutral = 3		Disagree = 2		Strongly Disagree =1		TOTAL		w \bar{x}	I
	F	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1. The school	80	74.77	24	22.43	3	2.80	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.72	SA

leader shows strong commitment to promoting inclusive practices.														
2. The administrator motivates teachers to implement inclusive strategies.	77	71.96	25	23.36	5	4.67	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.67	SA
3. Leadership decisions consistently consider the needs of learners with disabilities.	75	70.09	27	25.23	5	4.67	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.65	SA
4. Administrators collaborate with stakeholders to support inclusive education.	75	70.09	26	24.30	6	5.61	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.64	SA
5. The school head demonstrates effective problem-solving in managing inclusive education challenges.	73	68.22	31	28.97	3	2.80	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.65	SA
Total/General w\bar{x}	380	71.03	133	24.86	22	4.11	0	0	0	0	535	100	4.67	SA

Legend:

- | | | | | | |
|----------|-------------|----------------|----------|-------------|-------------------|
| 5 | 4.20 - 5.0 | Strongly Agree | 2 | 1.80 - 2.59 | Disagree |
| 4 | 3.40 - 4.19 | Agree | 1 | 1.0 - 1.79 | Strongly Disagree |
| 3 | 2.60 - 3.39 | Neutral | | | |

As shown in table 5, the survey findings revealed that the level of preparedness for School Administrators in inclusive education in terms of leadership skills commonly favorable view with the weighted mean score of 4.67. Significantly, the highest weighted mean of 4.72 emphasized that the school leader shows strong commitment to promoting inclusive practices. On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 4.64 gave emphasis that administrators collaborate with stakeholders to support inclusive education. This finding align with the study of Aragao (2025) that leadership attributes decision making, openness to change, motivational capability, and responsibility. The study also highlights leadership practices such as vision-setting, communication, relationship-building, and professionalism as essential drivers of inclusive school systems.

Fabunan and Cabal (2025) reported on the level of competence of school heads in implementing inclusive education. As shown in research effective instructional leadership is important to make sure inclusive education is promoted in schools. School Administrators established excellent proficiency in collaborating with teachers, reviewing student output and following the school policies that prioritize collaboration and respect for individual differences.

Table 6. Level of Preparedness of School Administrators in inclusive education in terms of Resource Allocation

Indicator	Strongly Agree = 5		Agree = 4		Neutral = 3		Disagree = 2		Strongly Disagree = 1		TOTAL		w \bar{x}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1. Resources for learners with special needs are adequately provided.	54	50.47	34	31.78	17	15.89	2	1.87	0	0	107	100	4.31	SA
2. Budget allocation includes support for inclusive education materials.	54	50.47	32	29.91	18	16.82	3	2.80	0	0	107	100	4.28	A
3. Assistive devices or learning tools are made available to students who need them.	52	48.60	34	31.78	18	16.82	3	2.80	0	0	107	100	4.26	A
4. Administrators ensure teachers have access to necessary instructional resources.	57	53.27	37	34.58	13	12.15	0	0.00	0	0	107	100	4.41	SA
5. Funding is allocated for training related to inclusive education.	57	53.27	37	34.58	13	12.15	0	0.00	0	0	107	100	4.41	SA
Total/General w\bar{x}	274	51.21	174	32.52	79	14.77	8	1.50	0	0	535	100	4.33	SA

Legend:

- 5 4.20 - 5.0 Strongly Agree 2 1.80 - 2.59 Disagree
4 3.40 - 4.19 Agree 1 1.0 - 1.79 Strongly Disagree
3 2.60 - 3.39 Neutral

The survey findings in table 6, indicated that the level of preparedness of school administrators in inclusive education in terms of resource allocation commonly accepted as positive as proven by the weighted mean score of 4.33 interpreted as strongly agree. Notably, the highest mean of 4.41 emphasized that administrators ensure teachers have access to necessary instructional resources and funding is allocated for training related to inclusive education. However, the lowest mean of 4.28 interpreted as agree highlighted the assistive devices or learning tools are made available to students who need them. This findings contrary to the study of Borja (2025) emphasized that resource insufficiency, including limited financial allocation for inclusive programs and shortages in specialized materials.

According to Steed et al. (2024), highlighted that administrators give importance to inclusion and make sure access to resources are possible but they still report limited funding and shortages of assistive devices and personnel.

Table 7. Level of Preparedness of School Administrators in inclusive education in terms of Professional Development

Indicator	Strongly Agree = 5		Agree = 4		Neutral = 3		Disagree = 2		Strongly Disagree = 1		TOTAL		w \bar{x}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1. Administrators provide opportunities for teachers to attend inclusion-related seminars.	65	60.75	38	35.51	2	1.87	2	1.87	0	0	107	100	4.55	SA
2. Professional development activities address diverse learning needs in the classroom.	65	60.75	35	32.71	4	3.74	3	2.80	0	0	107	100	4.51	SA
3. There is a school-wide plan for capacity-building on inclusive education.	58	54.21	40	37.38	5	4.67	4	3.74	0	0	107	100	4.42	SA
4. Administrators support teachers who pursue training on special education.	65	60.75	36	33.64	2	1.87	4	3.74	0	0	107	100	4.51	SA
5. Inclusive education topics are regularly included in INSET and LAC sessions.	63	58.88	38	35.51	2	1.87	4	3.74	0	0	107	100	4.50	SA
Total/General w\bar{x}	316	59.07	187	34.95	15	2.80	17	3.18	0	0	535	100	4.50	SA

Legend:

5 4.20 - 5.0 Strongly Agree 2 1.80 - 2.59 Disagree
4 3.40 -4.19 Agree 1 1.0 -1.79 Strongly Disagree
3 2.60-3.39 Neutral

As presented in table 7, the survey findings revealed that the level of preparedness of school administrators in inclusive education in terms of professional development have broad consensus approval with the weighted mean score of 4.50 interpreted as strongly agree. Remarkably, the highest mean of 4.55 highlighted that the administrators provide opportunities for teachers to attend inclusion-related seminars. On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 4.42 interpreted as strongly agree emphasized that there is a school-wide plan for capacity-building on inclusive education. Based on the study of Sabanal et al., (2025) teachers with more relevant professional development experience demonstrate significantly higher readiness for inclusion.

In addition, based on the study of White and Rojo-Ramos et al., (2022), highlighted that when school leaders actively promote inclusive practices and invest in professional development, mentoring, and collaborative learning, they provide teachers with essential competencies such as differentiation strategies and teamwork skills to effectively handle diverse classrooms.

Table 8. Level of Preparedness of School Administrators in inclusive education in terms of Infrastructure

Indicator	Strongly Agree = 5		Agree = 4		Neutral = 3		Disagree = 2		Strongly Disagree = 1		TOTAL		w \bar{x}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1. School facilities are accessible to learners with physical disabilities.	48	44.86	41	38.32	15	14.02	3	2.80	0	0	107	100	4.25	A
2. Classrooms are arranged to accommodate diverse learner needs.	63	58.88	32	29.91	9	8.41	3	2.80	0	0	107	100	4.45	SA
3. The school has ramps, rails, or other accessibility features.	47	43.93	38	35.51	13	12.15	9	8.41	0	0	107	100	4.15	A
4. Toilets and pathways are designed for easy access of learners with disabilities.	53	49.53	38	35.51	10	9.35	6	5.61	0	0	107	100	4.29	A
5. Learning environments are safe and supportive for all students.	55	51.40	42	39.25	8	7.48	2	1.87	0	0	107	100	4.40	SA
Total/General w\bar{x}	266	49.72	191	35.70	55	10.28	23	4.30	0	0	535	100	4.31	SA

Legend:

5	4.20 - 5.0	Strongly Agree	2	1.80 - 2.59	Disagree
4	3.40 - 4.19	Agree	1	1.0 - 1.79	Strongly Disagree
3	2.60 - 3.39	Neutral			

As shown in table 8, the survey findings revealed a positive assessment of the schools' infrastructure in inclusive education, as reflected in the overall weighted mean of 4.31, interpreted as 'Strongly Agree'. Respondents highly affirm that classrooms are arranged to accommodate diverse learner needs with a weighted mean of 4.45. On the other hand, respondents also strongly agreed that the school has ramps, rails or other accessibility features as the lowest weighted mean of 4.15 interpreted as 'Agree'. Based on the findings, infrastructure domain generally scored strongly agree but accessibility sub-indicators garnered lower mean which supports the study of Javier (2023) that infrastructure remains a partial weakness. According to Javier's study, facilities received only moderate ratings among surveyed schools.

According to Bansal (2021), the research findings showed that while principals had a decent understanding of inclusion, they did not believe that schools were prepared to accommodate students with disabilities. Lack of infrastructure and resources, special education and support services, parent non-cooperation, large class sizes, and behavioral problems with children with disabilities were the main concerns raised.

The results aligned to the study Simorangkir (2021), documented the gaps between supervisory standards and concrete facility accessibility in inclusive schools (e.g., ramps, toilets), signifying that lack of infrastructure compels administrators' capacity to provide inclusive commitments. The UNESCO (2020) background paper details universal design elements and emphasized implementation difficulties; it commends submission tools that administrators can influence to develop physical accessibility and safety for all learners.

Table 9. Level of Preparedness of Teachers in inclusive education in terms of Knowledge

Indicator	Strongly Agree = 5		Agree = 4		Neutral = 3		Disagree = 2		Strongly Disagree = 1		TOTAL		w \bar{x}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1. Understand the principles of inclusive education.	62	57.94	35	32.71	7	6.54	3	2.80	0	0	107	100	4.46	SA
2. Familiar with laws related to learners with special needs.	58	54.21	39	36.45	9	8.41	1	0.93	0	0	107	100	4.44	SA
3. Know how to identify learners who require additional support.	66	61.68	30	28.04	11	10.28	0	0.00	0	0	107	100	4.51	SA
4. Understand the diverse learning styles of students.	67	62.62	37	34.58	3	2.80	0	0.00	0	0	107	100	4.60	SA
5. Aware of appropriate interventions for learners with special needs.	65	60.75	28	26.17	12	11.21	2	1.87	0	0	107	100	4.46	SA
Total/General w\bar{x}	318	59.44	169	31.59	42	7.85	6	1.12	0	0	535	100	4.49	SA

Legend:

5	4.20 - 5.0	Strongly Agree	2	1.80 - 2.59	Disagree
4	3.40 -4.19	Agree	1	1.0 -1.79	Strongly Disagree
3	2.60-3.39	Neutral			

As presented in table 9, the results revealed a high level of teachers' preparedness in inclusive education, as shown by the general weighted mean of 4.49, interpreted as "Strongly Agree". Teachers strongly agreed that they know how to identify learners who require additional support with the highest weighted mean of 4.46, indicating that practical competence in recognizing diverse learning needs. Meanwhile, the survey also recorded the lowest weighted mean of 4.44 that emphasized the familiarity with the laws related to learners with special needs.

Overall, the consistently high scores across all indicators demonstrated that teachers feel well-prepared, knowledgeable and capable of implementing inclusive education effectively. This findings related to the study of Sabanal et.al (2025) stated that teachers with higher professional development exposure shows significantly have greater knowledge and understanding.

Effective inclusive education is built on the knowledge of teachers. Teachers had a modest understanding of inclusive education, especially when it came to inclusive teaching methods and managing students with a range of needs, according to a 2025 research by Vergara et al. Significant knowledge gaps still exist, nevertheless, in areas like implementing Individualized Education Plans (IEPs), adaptive technology, and Universal Design for Learning (UDL). These discrepancies point to the necessity of additional specialized training to improve educators' academic and practical comprehension of inclusive teaching frameworks.

Table 10. Level of Preparedness of Teachers in inclusive education in terms of Instructional Skills

Indicator	Strongly Agree = 5		Agree = 4		Neutral = 3		Disagree = 2		Strongly Disagree =1		TOTAL		w \bar{x}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1. Use differentiated instructional strategies to meet varied learning needs.	69	64.49	31	28.97	7	6.54	0	0.00	0	0.00	107	100	4.58	SA
2. Apply accommodations or modifications for learners with special needs.	60	56.07	39	36.45	6	5.61	2	1.87	0	0.00	107	100	4.47	SA
3. Contextualized learning materials that are tailored to the specific needs of the learners.	59	55.14	40	37.38	8	7.48	0	0.00	0	0.00	107	100	4.48	SA
4. Adjust classroom activities to support inclusive participation.	61	57.01	41	38.32	5	4.67	0	0.00	0	0.00	107	100	4.52	SA

5. Implement positive behavioral support strategies for diverse learners.	69	64.49	36	33.64	2	1.87	0	0.00	0	0.00	107	100	4.63	SA
Total/General w\bar{x}	318	59.44	187	34.95	28	5.23	2	0.37	0	0.00	535	100	4.53	SA

Legend:

5	4.20 - 5.0	Strongly Agree	2	1.80 - 2.59	Disagree
4	3.40 - 4.19	Agree	1	1.0 - 1.79	Strongly Disagree
3	2.60 - 3.39	Neutral			

As shown in Table 10, the survey findings showed that teachers' preparedness in terms of instructional skills was consistently strong with an overall weighted mean of 4.53, interpreted as "Strongly Agree". Respondents strongly agreed on the use of differentiated instructional strategies to meet varied learning needs with a weighted mean of 4.63, as the highest weighted mean. While, the lowest weighted mean garnered 4.47, indicated the implementation of positive behavioral support strategies for diverse learners.

This findings showed strong agreement with the study of Vergara et al. (2025) reported that teachers exhibit strengths in fostering inclusive teaching practices and managing classrooms through differentiated strategies, though they still require further support in adapting instruction to highly diverse or complex needs.

According to a study by Donath et al. (2023), professional development has a moderately positive impact on teachers' instructional skills. This suggests that when teachers receive structured training that incorporates practice-based and active learning components, their instructional readiness significantly improves.

Based on the study of Cola et al., (2025), findings discovered that the most highly ranked aspect of teacher readiness was instructional skills, which indicated that teachers felt most comfortable creating courses, adjusting their methods, and employing tactics for a variety of learners. Instructional strategies were strongly correlated with acceptance of inclusion, suggesting that better instructional skill reinforces willingness to teach inclusively.

Table 11. Level of Preparedness of Teachers in inclusive education in terms of Attitudes

Indicator	Strongly Agree = 5		Agree = 4		Neutral = 3		Disagree = 2		Strongly Disagree = 1		TOTAL		w \bar{x}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1. Patient and flexible when addressing diverse learning needs.	69	64.49	33	30.84	5	4.67	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.60	SA
2. Enjoy working in an inclusive classroom setting.	65	60.75	32	29.91	10	9.35	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.51	SA
3. Willing to adjust my teaching approach to ensure that learners with special needs feel included.	68	63.55	33	30.84	6	5.61	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.58	SA
4. Feel challenged	68	63.55	31	28.97	8	7.48	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.56	SA

and motivated in teaching an inclusive setting.														
5. Believing that all learners, regardless of disability, can succeed with proper support.	70	65.42	30	28.04	7	6.54	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.59	SA
Total/General w\bar{x}	340	63.55	159	29.72	36	6.73	0	0	0	0	535	100	4.57	SA

Legend:

- 5** 4.20 - 5.0 Strongly Agree **2** 1.80 - 2.59 Disagree
4 3.40 -4.19 Agree **1** 1.0 -1.79 Strongly Disagree
3 2.60-3.39 Neutral

As presented in table 11, the survey findings displayed teachers have very strong dispositional readiness for inclusive education with the general weighted mean of 4. 57 (Strongly Agree). Most respondents strongly agreed on having patient and flexible when addressing diverse learning needs which garnered the highest weighted mean of 4. 60. However, enjoy working in an inclusive classroom setting got the lowest weighted mean of 4. 51.

This findings supported by the study of Woodcock and Hardy (2025) found that teachers with high self-efficacy adopt more holistic and positive attitudes toward students with special needs, collaborate more effectively with peers, and engage more proactively in professional development. According to Singh et al., (2020), the study investigate the attitude of the teacher’s towards inclusive education. Educator attitudes toward inclusive education range from mild to positive, according to the study's findings.

To improve teachers' proficiency in inclusive education, continuous professional development, or CPD, is crucial. El Deen (2023) discovered that mentors' methods for evaluating teachers' performance and development differ, highlighting the difficulty of assessing professional development. Similar to this, Sebsibe et al. (2023) highlighted that a lack of suitable training modalities is the root cause of many instructional challenges, highlighting the necessity of supervisory assistance that encourages ongoing skill development.

Additionally, Holmqvist & Lelinge (2021) found that participation in professional development significantly enhances teachers’ attitudes toward inclusion. Interestingly, their study also revealed that teachers with the most positive attitudes show higher risks of burnout, indicating that attitude support must be accompanied by structural resources and psychological well-being.

Table 12. Level of Preparedness of Teachers in inclusive education in terms of Professional Development

Indicator	Strongly Agree = 5		Agree = 4		Neutral = 3		Disagree = 2		Strongly Disagree =1		TOTAL		w \bar{x}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1. Actively participate in trainings related to inclusive education.	60	56.07	37	34.58	8	7.48	2	1.87	0	0	107	100	4.45	SA
2. Seek	62	57.94	35	32.71	10	9.35	0	0.00	0	0	107	100	4.49	SA

opportunities to enhance my skills in handling learners with special needs.														
3. Updated on current trends and best practices in inclusive education.	62	57.94	37	34.58	3	2.80	5	4.67	0	0	107	100	4.46	SA
4. Integrate learning from seminars and workshops into my teaching.	64	59.81	35	32.71	8	7.48	0	0.00	0	0	107	100	4.52	SA
5. Collaborate with experts or resource persons to improve my inclusion practices.	66	61.68	32	29.91	9	8.41	0	0.00	0	0	107	100	4.53	SA
Total/General w\bar{x}	314	58.69	176	32.90	38	7.10	7	1.31	0	0	535	100	4.49	SA

Legend:

- 5** 4.20 - 5.0 Strongly Agree **2** 1.80 - 2.59 Disagree
- 4** 3.40 -4.19 Agree **1** 1.0 -1.79 Strongly Disagree
- 3** 2.60-3.39 Neutral

As shown in table 12, the data revealed that teachers demonstrated consistently strong commitment to professional development in inclusive education, as shown by the overall weighted mean of 4.49, interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. Teachers strongly collaborate with experts or resource persons to improve inclusion practices with the highest weighted mean of 4.53. On the other hand, the lowest rated-indicator with a weighted mean of 4.45 showed teachers actively participate in trainings related to inclusive education, indicating that willingness to engage in activities that enhance their competence in supporting diverse learners.

This findings supported by the study of Factor and Saenz (2025) reported that inclusive schools with strong teamwork, mentoring system and collaborative learning communities showed better professional development outcomes because teachers learn from one another and share best practices in real contexts.

Furthermore, Holmqvist & Lelling (2021) highlighted that collaborative professional development fosters collective responsibility and strengthens school wide inclusive practices. A shared professional learning environment enhances teachers’ confidence and preparedness, reinforcing that inclusion is most effective when teachers work with rather than in isolation.

Table 13. Level of Preparedness of Teachers in inclusive education in terms of Collaboration

Indicator	Strongly Agree = 5		Agree = 4		Neutral = 3		Disagree = 2		Strongly Disagree =1		TOTAL		w \bar{x}	I
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
1. Collaborate with special education teachers when	64	59.81	36	33.64	7	6.54	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.53	SA

needed.														
2. Communicate with parents/guardians about their child's needs.	72	67.29	33	30.84	2	1.87	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.65	SA
3. Work well with colleagues to plan inclusive activities.	69	64.49	32	29.91	6	5.61	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.59	SA
4. Seek advice from experts when facing challenges with special needs students.	69	64.49	33	30.84	5	4.67	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.60	SA
5. Participate in team discussions about improving inclusive practices.	73	68.22	32	29.91	2	1.87	0	0	0	0	107	100	4.66	SA
Total/General w\bar{x}	347	64.86	166	31.03	22	4.11	0	0	0	0	535	100	4.61	SA

Legend:

- 5 4.20 - 5.0 Strongly Agree 2 1.80 - 2.59 Disagree
4 3.40 - 4.19 Agree 1 1.0 - 1.79 Strongly Disagree
3 2.60 - 3.39 Neutral

Table 13 demonstrated that the survey revealed teachers' level of preparedness for inclusive education, which is significantly influenced by the general weighted average of 4.61. The highest-rated indicator, participation in team discussions about improving inclusive practices garnered a weighted mean of 4.66, this reflects strong culture of teamwork, shared decision-making and collective responsibility within the school. Nevertheless, the lowest-rated indicator, collaboration with special needs education teachers when needed with the weighted mean of 4.53, suggesting a strong recognition of the importance of shared expertise in addressing learners' diverse needs.

This findings supported by the study of Javier (2023) noted that during the execution of inclusive education programs, educators often rely on collaboration with colleagues, school leaders and specialist to overcome challenges in instructional materials, training gaps and resource limitations. Her findings further support collaboration as a compensatory mechanism where teachers' shared expertise becomes an important tool for problem-solving and maintaining inclusive learning environments.

Table 14. Comparative Summary of the Level of Preparedness of School Administrators for Inclusive Education

School Administrators	Overall	Interpretation
Policies	4.69	Strongly Agree
Leadership skills	4.67	Strongly Agree
Professional Development	4.50	Strongly Agree
Resource Allocation	4.33	Strongly Agree
Infrastructure	4.31	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.50	Strongly Agree

Table 14 provides the summary of the overall mean for the five indicators of the level of preparedness of school administrators for inclusive education in the elementary schools of District

II. The data revealed an overall average of 4.50, which is interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. This suggests that school administrators exhibited a very high level of preparedness for inclusive education across all indicators. Policies collected the highest weighted mean of 4.69, which is interpreted as “Strongly Agree” among all domains. The results suggesting that administrators strongly affirm the presence of and implementation of clear and supportive policies for inclusive education. Infrastructure gathered the lowest weighted mean of 4.31, which is interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. This indicator received the lowest mean among the five, yet it remains with the “Strongly Agree” range, suggesting that school facilities are generally supportive of the inclusive education, though there may be still be room for improvement compared to other areas.

Table 15. Comparative Summary of the Level of Preparedness of Teachers for Inclusive Education

Teachers	Overall	Interpretation
Collaboration	4.61	Strongly Agree
Attitudes	4.57	Strongly Agree
Instructional Skills	4.53	Strongly Agree
Knowledge	4.49	Strongly Agree
Professional Development	4.49	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.54	Strongly Agree

In table 15, data revealed that teachers established a very high level of preparedness for inclusive education, as supported by the overall mean of 4.54, interpreted as Strong Agree. This displays that teachers perceive themselves as well- prepared and equipped to implement inclusive practices in their respective classrooms. Collaboration obtained the highest mean of 4.61, indicating that teachers highly value and actively participate in collaboration with colleagues, parents and Sped teachers to support inclusive education. Knowledge and Professional development both collected a weighted mean of 4.49 as the lowest mean among all indicators yet it remains within the strongly agree range. This indicates teachers should continue to strengthen and enhance further their inclusive education practices.

Table 16. Results on Relationship of the level of preparedness of School Administrators and level of preparedness of teachers in inclusive education

n =107

Variables	r	I	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of preparedness of School Administrators and level of preparedness of teachers	0.999	Very High Correlation	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

0.5 level of significance

The table 16 presented the results of the correlation test results concerning variables. The computed Pearson r value of 0.999 indicated a very high correlation between the level of preparedness of school administrators and those of teachers in inclusive education.

However, when subjected to test of significance using probability value, the p-value obtained is 0.001 which is lower than the level of significance of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that there exists a significant relationship between the preparedness levels of school administrators and preparedness levels of teachers for inclusive education.

CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter provides the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations of the study on Administrators' Preparedness and Teachers' Preparedness for Inclusive Education in District II, Division of San Carlos City.

Summary of Findings

The study "Administrators' Preparedness and Teachers' Preparedness for Inclusive Education in the Elementary Schools District II, Division of San Carlos City", used the descriptive-correlational method. The research includes 4 questions uncovering statistical relationships between school administrators' preparedness and teachers' preparedness for inclusive education in District II, Division of San Carlos City.

The aim of the research was to investigate the correlation between the school administrators' preparedness and teachers' preparedness for inclusive education in District II, Division of San Carlos City.

Based on the survey findings, it was revealed that school administrators exhibited an exceptional high degree of preparedness across all domains of inclusive education implementation in terms of the following indicators as evidenced by their weighted mean scores, which consistently surpassed 3.39.

With regular monitoring guaranteeing their efficacy, policies received a weighted mean of 4.69, which is taken as strongly agreeing that they are clear, updated, and closely matched with DepEd recommendations. Leadership skills obtained a weighted mean of 4.67, which is deemed strongly agree, and showed a dedicated and inspiring leadership style while making sure that the requirements of students with disabilities were taken into account when making decisions. With schools offering enough funds, teaching materials, and vital resources, resource allocation received a weighted mean of 4.33, which is taken as strongly agreeing that it is generally enough. However, the somewhat lower rating for assistive devices indicates that this is an area that need more attention.

Administrators' efforts to provide ongoing training, capacity building activities, and the incorporation of inclusive education subjects within INSET and LAC sessions are reflected in the weighted mean of 4.50 for professional development, which is read as strongly agreeing that it works well. Infrastructure had a weighted mean score of 4.31, which indicates good agreement with the findings that it supports inclusive practices. However, several accessibility elements, including handrails and ramps, might be improved to better serve the needs of all students.

As demonstrated by their weighted mean scores, which continuously above 3.39, the research findings showed that instructors were extremely well-prepared for inclusive education in terms of the following categories.

Teachers' understanding of identifying students with special needs, interventions, legislation, and inclusive principles was demonstrated by their total weighted mean score of 4.49, which is understood as highly agree. The total weighted average of 4.53 for instructional skills, which is read as highly agree, demonstrated that instructors are capable of successfully managing diverse classes, applying accommodations, and differentiating teaching.

Attitudes acquired an general weighted mean of 4.57, which is interpreted as strongly agree emphasized that teachers showed highly positive attitudes, patience, and willingness to adjust for learner needs. Professional Development collected an overall weighted mean of 4.49, interpreted as strongly agree demonstrated that teachers participated in trainings and seek opportunities to improve inclusive instruction. Collaboration earned an general weighted mean of 4.61, interpreted

as strongly agree revealed that teachers frequently engage in team discussions, collaborate with SPED teachers, and communicate with parents.

As shown in the research findings, there was a significant relationship that existed between school administrator's preparedness and teachers' preparedness for inclusive education in District II, San Carlos City as indicated in the computed value of 0.999 yielded by Pearson r, there was a very high correlation established.

However, when subjected to test of significance using probability value, the p-value obtained is 0.001 which is lower than the level of significance of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that there exists a significant relationship between the preparedness levels of school administrators and those of teachers for inclusive education.

Despite the findings indicating a strong correlation between the preparedness levels of school administrators and level of preparedness and those of teachers for inclusive education, but still the researcher decided to implement a Professional Development Training Program particularly in District II, Division of San Carlos City. This training program enhance professional competencies of administrators and teachers in implementing inclusive education.

Conclusion

School administrators and teachers in District II are both very well-prepared for inclusive education, suggesting a strong basis that can handle a variety of kids. Teacher readiness is significantly influenced by administrative preparation, as seen by the findings that teachers exhibit higher levels of competence and confidence when school administrators provide clear policies, good leadership, sufficient resources, and continual professional development.

Although the district has implemented several inclusive practices, there is still need for improvement in areas like the availability of assistive devices and the availability of school facilities. The capability of teachers and the assistance they receive from school administrators are significantly correlated, suggesting that increases in leadership and resource accessibility enhance teachers' capability to address the needs of students with disabilities.

In general, District II schools are prepared to manage inclusive education; but, in order to guarantee completely fair and inclusive learning environments, they must keep improving facility accessibility and resource availability.

Recommendation

In light of the conclusions derived from the findings of this study, recommendations may be offered to enhance education.

School administrators should strengthen policies, enhance leadership and ensure inclusion remains a school priority by developing features of accessibility, upgrading the assistive devices and allocating funds to further strengthen the implementation of inclusive education. Professional development such as INSET's, LAC Sessions, regular coaching and mentoring should be given emphasis. Furthermore, it is vital to nurture cooperation between general education and SPED teachers in order to ensure constant and effective implementation of inclusive strategies.

Teachers should continue enhancing their knowledge, instructional capabilities through actively engaging in seminars and trainings related to inclusive education. They should also enhance collaboration with SPED Teachers, guidance counselor, and parents/ guardians in order to guarantee that interventions for learners with special need are well coordinated and open to learners needs.

Learners with disabilities should be encourage to join in school activities, use available support services and share their desires with the help of the teachers and parents. When teachers shows

strong disposition, collaboration and instructional abilities, learners can use from individualized interventions, spaces and assistive devices provided by the school.

Parents and guardians are urged to collaborate with the school by supporting school programs at home and participating in inclusive education meetings, consultation and activities. Their active involvement sustained by school orientation and clear communication can help ensure continuous support for learners with disabilities and reinforces their general development.

Future researchers should examine the other aspects affecting inclusive education like school culture, parental involvement and mental supports, learners output and assistive devices and the may utilize a qualitative approach to explore the lived experiences of educators, administrators and learners. They may develop the study to other areas for wider generalizability and assess the prosed professional development program to identify its impact on teachers' competence and learners' outcome.

DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

DISTRICT II PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT TRAINING PROGRAM MATRIX

Program Title: Strengthening Inclusive Education Preparedness for School Administrators and Teachers in District II

RATIONALE: Given the very high correlation found between the preparedness of school administrators and teachers for inclusive education, this training program aims to enhance both groups' competencies in policy implementation, instructional practices, collaboration, and inclusive learning environments. Supporting both administrators and teachers simultaneously ensures aligned practices, consistent decision-making, and improved support for learners with disabilities.

Suggested Duration: 3–5 days (plus follow-up LAC sessions)

Participants: All School administrators, master teachers, general and SPED teachers, guidance personnel

Modality: Face-to-face with school-based application tasks and LAC follow-through

Module	Objectives	Core Content	Training Strategies/Activities	Evaluation & Evidence of Learning
1. Orientation on IE Policies & Standards	1) Deepen understanding of DepEd IE policies and global frameworks. 2) Align school practices with policy requirements.	DepEd Orders on IE; Roles of admins & teachers.	Policy walkthrough; compliance checklist workshop; group synthesis.	Completed checklist; quiz; commitment statements.
2. Leadership for Inclusive Schools	Strengthen inclusive leadership and shared decision-making.	Inclusive leadership competencies; data-informed decisions; motivational strategies.	Case analysis; leadership reflection tool; create action plan.	Leadership action plan; reflection notes.
3. Differentiated Instruction & UDL	Equip teachers with UDL-based lesson design and admin coaching skills.	UDL principles; differentiation strategies; inclusive assessment.	Lesson plan workshop; demo teaching; peer feedback.	Revised lesson plans; observation checklist; micro-teaching.
4. Collaboration	Improve multi-	IEP components;	IEP simulation; role-	Sample IEP;

& IEP Processes	stakeholder collaboration and IEP development.	case conferencing; referral protocols.	play; communication planning.	facilitation checklist; communication plan.
5. Resource Allocation & Assistive Technology	Prioritize budgets/resources and build familiarity with assistive devices.	Budgeting; categories of assistive tech; low-cost adaptations.	AT stations; resource mapping; budget workshop.	AT utilization plan; procurement list; budget items.
6. Inclusive Infrastructure & Environment	Assess and improve accessibility and classroom organization.	Accessibility standards; classroom layout; safety protocols.	Accessibility audit; redesign challenge; documentation.	Audit report; layout plans; improvement timeline.
7. Monitoring, Evaluation & Continuous Improvement	Build systems for tracking preparedness and IE outcomes.	Indicators/tools; data capture; LAC integration.	Develop M&E tools; data-use clinic; school plan drafting.	M&E toolset; data template; IE development plan.

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